

Influence of organic fertilizers on changes in soil properties under open and protected cultivation practices

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on Jan 08, 2020 Revised on Feb 16, 2020 Accepted on Feb 25, 2020 Published on March 24, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Shree Prasad Vista, Dipak Kumar Jha Corresponding Author Email prasadvista@rediffmail.com</p>	<p>An experiment conducted to evaluate the influence of different organic manure on soil properties under glasshouse and open field condition at Khumaltar, Lalitpur during 2017-2018 showed insignificant results on major soil properties by the application of different organic manure under open and protected environmental condition at varying sampling days. The experiment was laid out in Complete Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications and six treatments <i>viz.</i> Vermicompost (VC) @ 10:1 gkg⁻¹ of soil (T₁), FYM @ 10:1 gkg⁻¹ of soil (T₂), Poultry Manure (PM) @ 10:1 gkg⁻¹ of soil (T₃), Safal Kishan (SK) @ 10:1 gkg⁻¹ of soil (T₄), Nepalese Organic Fertilizer (NOF) @ 10:1 gkg⁻¹ of soil (T₅) and Control (T₆). Application of poultry manure and Safal kisan under glasshouse condition recorded higher organic matter (6.40 %) at 90 days and application of poultry manure under open condition at 30 days recorded higher total Nitrogen Content (0.53%). Application of vermicompost and poultry manure under open condition at 60 days have highest available Phosphorous content (381 kg ha⁻¹), whereas application of poultry manure under open condition at 60 days was observed having highest available potassium content (782 kg ha⁻¹) in the soil.</p>
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Production of agriculture commodities depend upon various input factors for getting good expected output. Fertilizer is one of the major factors for the good agriculture production and its role is directly or indirectly reflected to the growth and development of the plants. Vegetables and high value crops are generally grown under protected condition. Under the open field conditions, only the seasonal vegetables can be grown due to their climatic condition requirement for the growth and development while under the protected (glasshouse/plastic tunnel) condition both seasonal and off seasonal vegetables can be grown by maintaining the favorable condition for the growth of plants. Under the protected condition quality of

the produced crop can be maintained better than the open field condition. The yield under the protected condition can be achieved to the level of 4 to 8 times more as compared to open field crop cultivation (Agri Farming, 2017). Generally, vegetables are highly responsive to organic sources of nutrients and profitable to farmers. The organic sources of manures/fertilizer besides supplying N, P, and K also make unavailable sources of elemental nitrogen, bound phosphates, micronutrients, and decomposed plant residues into an available form to facilitate the plants to absorb the nutrients. The soil properties, microbial activities, and characteristic of soil will vary with the variation in temperature, irrigation/rainfall, and management practices

(especially organic or inorganic). The present study was designed to know the effect of various organic manures on properties of soil under two different environmental conditions. The main purpose of this study was to study detailed information on changes in different chemical properties of soil parameters by the application of different organic sources of manures under open field and glasshouse condition at different time interval.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted to study the effect of different types of organic manures on changes in soil properties under open field and glasshouse condition. The effort has been made to know the change in soil properties after organic manures application to make the relationship between nutrient releasing pattern and availability to plants. The research was carried out at a glasshouse and an open field near to glasshouse of Soil Science Division of NARC, Khumaltar, Lalitpur in Complete Randomized Design with the following treatment combinations.

- T₁: Ratio of Vermicompost and soil @1:100 (30g VC in 3 kg soil)
- T₂: Ratio of FYM and soil @ 1:100 (30g FYM in 3 kg soil)
- T₃: Ratio of Poultry manure and soil @ 1:100 (30g PM in 3 kg soil)
- T₄: Ratio of Safal Kishan and soil @ 1:100 (30g SK in 3 kg soil)
- T₅: Ratio of Nepalese Organic Fertilizer (NOF) and soil @ 1:100 (30g NOF in 3 kg soil)
- T₆: No application of organic manures (control)

The treatments were replicated thrice. Soil analysis was done periodically for 90 days following standard procedure and the data were analyzed using Genstat statistical software. The relevant properties of the soil used for the study are shown in table 1.

Preparation of Soil

The experiment was carried out in glasshouse and open field at Khumaltar. Soil was collected from the field nearby which was thoroughly mixed and soil was weighed and then taken as per requirement of the treatment. Different types of organic manures were applied to each treatment. Each pot was seeded with 3 seeds of french bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) var. four seasons bean. All the treatments were then left for 90 days

and required parameters were recorded. Soil samples of all treatments were collected 3 times after the application of all of the respective treatments at 30, 60 and 90 days for the estimation of soil chemical properties.

Results and Discussion

Soil Properties: Soil Reaction

In general, the soil reaction increased with the period of the investigation till 60 days and then it showed decreasing trend. In all the treatments the pH increased over time in the both cases and this may be due to organic manure and cropping. The cropping releases root exudates that are utilized by the microorganisms as food materials and thereby increase soil pH. The changes in soil pH at 30 days were highly significant under glasshouse condition. The soil pH was observed significantly differ with treatments upto 60 days. Higher order of soil pH was observed in the soil treated with Safal Kishan in all stages of sampling whereas the lowest soil pH was observed in controlled pots in early stage of the crop growth. However, in the later stage, FYM showed low pH. In general, application of Organic manures and cropping increases soil pH.

Closer observation of data reveals that application of different types of organic manures in open field and glasshouse condition has positive influence in soil pH. Application of organic manures contributes to increase in pH of soil for sometimes and then after the pH of soil again goes on decreasing. Application of organic manures in open field condition has higher influence on soil pH increment as compared to glasshouse condition this is because in the glasshouse condition there is quick mineralization of the applied manures due more favourable condition (high temperature and relative humidity) as compared to field condition. In the open field condition mineralization of the applied manures occur at slower rate which tend to change the pH of the soil to the long term.

Organic Matter Content in Soil

Perusal of data reveals that in general, OM decreases with period of experiment in both condition of all treatments. This may due to the quick mineralization at early stage. There is sharp increase in organic matter after 60 days in all treatments.

Table 1. Soil properties of the experimental site

S. N.	Soil Parameters	Results	Methods of Analysis
1	Soil pH	5.6	Digital pHmeter
2	Organic matter (OM)%	4.98	Walkley-Black method
3	Total N (%)	0.007	Kjeldahl Digestion method
4	Available Phosphorous (P ₂ O ₅ kg ha ⁻¹)	6.48	Modified Olsen's Bicarbonate method
5	Available Potassium(K ₂ O kg ha ⁻¹)	162.3	Flame photometric method

Appendix 1. Effect of different types of organic manures on soil chemical properties

a) Organic Matter

Treatments	Soil OM % at Different Interval							Mean	OM %
	0 Day	30 Days		60 Days		90 Days			
		GH	OF	GH	OF	GH	OF		
T ₁ : VC	4.98	1.68	2.7	0.19	0.443	3.68	4.41	1.85	2.52
T ₂ :FYM	4.98	3.39	2.78	0.93	0.413	4.41	1.17	2.91	1.45
T ₃ :PM	4.98	1.32	1.38	0.148	0.347	6.40	3.72	2.62	1.82
T ₄ :SK	4.98	1.65	2.39	0.157	0.5	6.40	4.18	2.74	2.36
T ₅ :NOF	4.98	4.05	1.5	0.1	0.46	5.77	2.37	3.31	1.44
T ₆ :Control	4.98	2.47	3.28	0.253	0.23	4.67	1.55	2.46	1.68
SEM		0.149	0.427	0.058	0.097	0.805	1.194		
CV%		0.7	35.4	25.5	3.1	9.3	40.7		
P-value		<.001	0.06	0.583	0.462	0.166	0.317		
LSD		0.47	1.346	0.1838	0.3059	2.53	3.76		

b) Total Nitrogen Content in Soil

Treatments	TN % at Different Interval							Mean TN %	
	0 Day	30 Days		60 Days		90 Days		GH	OF
		GH	OF	GH	OF	GH	OF		
T ₁ : VC	0.007	0.26	0.4	0.06	0.03	0.10	0.02	0.13	0.15
T ₂ :FYM	0.007	0.43	0.45	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.16	0.16
T ₃ :PM	0.007	0.52	0.53	0.03	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.21	0.21
T ₄ :SK	0.007	0.38	0.43	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.16
T ₅ :NOF	0.007	0.36	0.43	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.13	0.16
T ₆ :Control	0.007	0.34	0.25	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.13	0.09
SEM		0.022	0.017	0.011	0.014	0.008	0.008		
CV%		2.5	3.3	59.2	17.2	64.7	30.7		
F-value		<.001	<.001	0.147	0.034	0.08	0.052		
LSD		0.70	0.053	0.035	0.046	0.026	0.026		

c) Available Phosphorous Content in Soil

Treatments	P ₂ O ₅ kgha ⁻¹ at Different Interval							Mean P ₂ O ₅ kgha ⁻¹	
	0 Day	30 Days		60 Days		90 Days		GH	OF
		GH	OF	GH	OF	GH	OF		
T ₁ : VC	6.48	118.6	176	103	381	68.1	44.9	96.57	200.63
T ₂ :FYM	6.48	121.1	278	100	362	97.6	185.5	106.23	275.17
T ₃ :PM	6.48	184.3	266	173	381	6.2	328.5	121.17	325.17
T ₄ :SK	6.48	158.6	255	149	366	11.4	95.3	106.33	238.77
T ₅ :NOF	6.48	110.5	265	186	309	15.3	266.5	103.93	280.17
T ₆ :Control	6.48	141	268	153	215	139.8	30.8	144.6	171.27
SEM		20.5	35.4	27.8	24.7	19.88	22.74		
CV%		6.5	12.3	15.7	6.7	10.3	10.5		
P-value		0.182	0.406	0.242	0.005	0.03	<.001		
LSD		64.6	111.6	87.4	77.9	62.64	71.65		

d) Available Potassium Content in Soil

Treatments	K ₂ O Kg ha ⁻¹ at Different Interval							Mean K ₂ O kg ha ⁻¹	
	0 Day	30 Days		60 Days		90 Days		GH	OF
		GH	OF	GH	OF	GH	OF		
T ₁ : VC	162.3	378	604	388	632	339	611	368.33	615.67
T ₂ : FYM	162.3	369	547	416	491	321	392	368.67	476.67
T ₃ : PM	162.3	660	651	491	782	444	611	531.67	681.33
T ₄ : SK	162.3	359	500	322	528	392	506	357.67	511.33
T ₅ : NOF	162.3	303	453	303	435	313	506	306.33	464.67
T ₆ : Control	162.3	219	311	200	430	300	374	239.67	371.67
SEM		52.2	63.7	42.4	160	36.6	79.7		
CV%		16.4	5.1	16.6	23.2	7.9	20.3		
P-value		0.003	0.041	0.010	0.52	0.121	0.234		
LSD		164.4	200.6	133.5	504	115.2	251		

e) Soil Reaction

Treatments	Soil P ^h At Different Interval							Mean pH	
	0 Day	30 Days		60 Days		90 Days		GH	OF
		GH	OF	GH	OF	GH	OF		
T ₁ : VC	5.6	6.08	6.30	6.82	6.82	6.54	6.86	6.48	6.66
T ₂ : FYM	5.6	5.94	6.01	6.61	6.65	6.49	6.52	6.35	6.39
T ₃ : PM	5.6	6.15	6.14	6.40	6.97	6.84	6.73	6.46	6.61
T ₄ : SK	5.6	6.52	6.65	7.05	7.32	7.10	6.76	6.89	6.91
T ₅ : NOF	5.6	6.24	6.20	6.93	6.79	6.91	6.71	6.69	6.57
T ₆ : Control	5.6	5.83	6.00	6.59	6.73	6.74	6.53	6.39	6.42
SEM		0.064	0.1814	0.082	0.142	0.153	1.16		
CV%		1.7	1.2	3.3	1.4	0.09	0.7		
P-value		<.001	0.041	0.039	0.010	0.126	0.369		
LSD		.2027	0.4042	0.259	0.3171	0.482	0.3782		

This may be due to decomposition of plants roots and roots exudates. The microbial population increases with the application of the organic manures and at later stage they die resulting higher OM in 90 days in all treatments under both conditions. For the sample collected at 30 days for all treatments, it was found that all the treatments have low organic matter content in both conditions of treatments application. At 30 days, the mean organic matter was found highest (4.05 %) in the soil treated with NOF under glasshouse. Compared to all other treatments, the lowest was found in poultry manure treated soil (1.32%). For the samples collected at 60 and 90 days, it showed similar pattern of differences in soil organic matter content with respect to different organic manure treatments in both conditions. In 60 days sampling soil organic matter content was in decreasing trend which again increased at 90 days. However, in 90 days, the highest organic matter content (6.4%) was found in the soil treated with poultry manure and Safal Kishan under glasshouse condition but lowest organic matter content (0.5%) was observed in the soil treated with Safal Kishan under open field condition at 60 days sampling and this was recorded to be the lowest organic matter content during the

experiment. Soil organic matter is one of the important properties of soil which influence the availability of water, macro and micronutrient for the growing plants and it also affects microbial activities in the soil. Soil organic matter contributes to the soil fertility with its decomposition by the various groups of microbes. In general, it is assumed that application of organic manures increases the soil organic matter content but the observation was contrary to our assumptions. Soil organic matter content was in decreasing trend up to 60 days and thereafter increased in both the conditions due to the quick mineralization at early stage and decomposition of plants roots and roots exudates in later stage resulting increase in soil OM.

Total Nitrogen Content in Soil

The total nitrogen content in soil was found significant with respect to different types of organic manures in glasshouse up to 30 days and up to 60 days in open field condition. Data reveal that all the treatments have high insignificant effect on total nitrogen content after 60 days in both environmental conditions. For the samples collected at 30 days, the mean total nitrogen was found highest (0.53 %) in the soil treated with poultry manure (PM) of open

field condition. The lowest total nitrogen content (0.25%) was observed in control treatment of open field condition. The effect of 4th and 5th treatments of open field condition on total nitrogen content was same as the value of 0.43%. At 60 days, the total nitrogen was highest (0.08%) in the soil treated with poultry manure and lowest in control plot under both conditions.

Available Phosphorous Content in Soil

The data of available phosphorous reveals that in general, soil available phosphorous was found insignificant with respect to different types of organic manures in both glasshouse and open field condition. However, higher available phosphorous content was observed in soil treated with vermicompost and poultry manure at 60 days under open field environmental condition. At 30 days, the mean available soil phosphorous was found highest (278 kg ha⁻¹) in soil treated with FYM under open field condition but in field condition it was observed higher (110.5 kg ha⁻¹) in soil treated with Nepalese Organic Fertilizer. At 60 days, available soil Phosphorous recorded highest (381 kg ha⁻¹) the soil treated with vermicompost and poultry manure under open field condition. The soil sample collected at 90 days showed the similar type of pattern of difference in available phosphorous level with respect to different treatments.

Available Potassium Content in Soil

Available potassium content in soil was found significant with respect to various organic manures treatments up to 60 days in glasshouse condition and up to 30 DAS in open field condition and after that all treatments have insignificant effect on available soil potassium content under both conditions. However, despite of being insignificant the data revealed that potassium content was higher in poultry manure treated soil than that of other organic manure treated soil in both of the case at all sampling days. At 30 days, the mean available soil potassium content was found highest (660 kg ha⁻¹) in the soil treated with poultry manure under glasshouse condition and lowest was observed in the controlled plots (219 kg ha⁻¹). At 60 days, available soil potassium was recorded highest (782 kg ha⁻¹) in the soil treated with poultry manure under open field condition and lowest in the controlled soil. At 90

days, similar pattern of results was obtained, however in this case highest mean available soil potassium were found in soils treated with vermicompost and poultry manure (611 kg ha⁻¹) and lowest in controlled soil.

Summary and Conclusion

The study was carried out to determine the influence of different types of organic manures on soil properties (N, P, K, OM % and pH) under two different environmental conditions. In general there is significant interaction between different types of organic manures and soil reaction with sampling days. There is significant influence of different organic manures on soil pH, the soil reaction increases with increase in the investigation period in both conditions. Soil organic matter content decreased with increase in the experimental period. Total nitrogen content and available phosphorus content in soil was found insignificant with respect to different types of organic manures in both glasshouse and open field condition. Available potassium content in soil was found significant with respect to various organic manures treatments up to 60 days in glasshouse condition and up to 30 days in open field condition.

From this study it can be concluded that the application of different types of the organic manures does not result into much changes in the soil chemical properties under open field and glasshouse conditions. Application of different organic manures result in increase in soil pH, OM, TN, P and K content of the soil earlier in the glasshouse as compared to the open field. Organic manures are eco-friendly and their advantages on soil properties can be easily seen in long term in the open field condition as compared to the protected condition.

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